

Kinetics of Competitive Adsorption :
Part IV : Bromide and Iodide Ions on Silver and Aluminium and
Chloride and Iodide Ions on Aluminium

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Adopting the technique reported earlier the competitive adsorption of Br⁻ and I⁻ ions on silver and aluminium and of Cl⁻ and I⁻ ions on aluminium has been studied, using ³⁶Cl, ⁸²Br and ¹³¹I for labelling the systems. The present results on the kinetic data for adsorption from binary halide ion mixtures confirm the earlier finding of a mutual suppression of a given halide ion adsorption due to the presence of another halide ion. The suppression is particularly heavy in the case of Br⁻ (> 90%) and I⁻ ions (80%) in the case of their adsorption on both the metals. These results are consistent with the observed relative rates of desorption of the halide ion by solutions of other halide ions.

Work on adsorption and desorption rates at solid-liquid interface prior to equilibrium¹⁻⁵ has been possible by the use of radio-tracer technique. The technique has also been used in the study of simultaneous or competitive adsorption between adsorbate ions on a given adsorbent surface. Earlier work on competitive adsorption has been limited to SO₄²⁻, Cl⁻ and CrO₄²⁻ ions on Fe²⁺; CN⁻ and I⁻ ions on Ag, Pt and Ni⁵; and I⁻ and PO₄³⁻ ions on Cu⁴; and our work on I⁻ and Cl⁻ ions on Ag⁶ and Cl⁻ and Br⁻ ions on Ag and Al⁷.

We had reported earlier^{6,7} that in the mixed adsorbates of Cl⁻ and Br⁻ or of Cl⁻ and I⁻ there is a heavy suppression (60% and above) of the adsorption of each ion due to the presence of the other ion. The study is extended to the simultaneous adsorption of Br⁻ and I⁻ ions on silver and aluminium and of I⁻ and Cl⁻ ions on aluminium.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

The radioisotopes used for labelling the system *viz.* ³⁶Cl (period 3.1 × 10⁵ yr), ⁸²Br (period 36 hr) and ¹³¹I (period 8.04 days) were supplied by the B.A.R.C., Bombay. The ³⁶Cl in the form of HCl had a specific activity of 391 μCi/g Cl while ⁸²Br in the form of NH₄Br had a specific activity of 128 mCi/g Br. The ¹³¹I was carrier-free with an activity of 5mCi/ml initially. These solutions were diluted and carefully calculated amounts were added to the adsorbate so as to give 2500 nett cpm per 0.1 ml of the solution. With a metal coupon (silver or aluminium) of area 3.14 cm² containing approximately 3.8 × 10¹⁵ atoms of the metal on the surface should correspond to 160 cpm if a monomolecular layer is formed by the labelled adsorbate of above specific activity. The pH was adjusted in all the cases to 3.5.

The experimental details for studying adsorption kinetics from labelled adsorbates and the measurement of layer-thickness have been described earlier.^{3,4,6} Foils of silver and aluminium, polished physically and chemically as per standard procedure^{6,7}, were taken as circular coupons ($d = 19.9$ mm). The adsorbate consisted of $10^{-3}M$ solutions of (i) NaI (^{131}I), (ii) a mixture of NaBr (^{82}Br) and NaI (^{131}I) and (iii) a mixture of NaI (^{131}I) and NaCl (^{36}Cl); all solutions being initially adjusted to pH 3.5 and maintained at 30° . Adsorption measurements were made for periods extending from 1 min to 200 hr employing separate coupons for each period. Individual activities in the doubly labelled solution of I^- and Br^- ions (^{131}I of period 8.04 days and ^{82}Br of period 36 hr) were determined from two measurements of the activities a_1 initial, and a_2 after 36 hr, the two being related as follows :

$$a_1 = a_I + a_{Br}, \quad a_2 = 0.88a_I + 0.5a_{Br}.$$

Likewise in the case of mixture of Cl^- and I^- ions the individual activities are obtainable from two measurements taken with the time interval of 8.04 days. The rate growth of adsorbed layer in each case is shown graphically in Figs. 1 and 2.

Fig. 1. Rates of adsorption on silver of (i) (A) Br^- , (B) I^- ions from $10^{-3}M$ NaBr and NaI solutions respectively and (ii) (C) I^- ions from (NaI+NaBr) solution, each $10^{-3}M$. All solutions of $pH = 3.5$ and $t = 30^\circ$.

Desorption with respect to mono-layer thickness of the I^- ions, adsorbed on aluminium, was studied in 100 ml of solutions of NaI, NaBr, NaCl ($10^{-3}M$, $pH = 3.5$) and water, maintained at 30° . The first order rate constants were calculated as before^{6,7} from the straight line plots of $\log(1-F)$ versus time, where F is the ratio of the activity desorbed at time t to that desorbed at steady state.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In these very dilute solutions of the adsorbate the formation of trace amounts of free halogen due to oxidation of the halide ions by the dissolved oxygen is not ruled out. Any trace of free halogen thus produced near the metal surface may be expected to react with the latter chemically. The results of earlier workers lend support to such chemical reactions *viz.*, formation of AgI^8 , AlI_3^{10} and $AlBr_3^{11}$ when these metals are immersed in the corresponding halogen solutions. In a preliminary experiment 25 ml of the labelled solution to be used later as adsorbate was shaken up with an equal volume of carbontetrachloride. No measurable activity could be detected in the organic layer even after a long interval which shows that the amount of free halogen produced could not be appreciable. Thus it would appear that the labelled halogen in the adsorbate is mainly in ionic form.

(A) *Adsorption on silver of Br^- and I^- ions*: The adsorption rate isotherms for Br^- and I^- ions on Ag differ appreciably. The iodide isotherm shows marked discontinuities indicated by a very sharp rise on the completion of about 100 layers in 100 hr, the maximum adsorption obtained being about 270 layers. The isotherm for Br^- ions is distinctly concave towards the time axis, showing a maximum adsorption of about 800 layers. The growth rate curves (Fig. 1) of adsorption from I^- - Br^- ion mixture shows that the I^- ions occupy all available adsorbent sites, the adsorption of Br^- ions in the mixture being nearly completely suppressed. Thus, from the I^- - Br^- ions mixed adsorbate, the adsorption of I^- ions proceeds uniquely for the first 100 hr, as if the adsorbates were one of pure I^- ions. The presence of Br^- ions is, however, felt at a later stage, after about 100 hr, when the subsequent adsorption of I^- ions is lowered by about 30%. The adsorption of Br^- ions is, however, completely suppressed all through. Thus, considering the overall adsorption it appears that each halide ion suppresses the adsorption of the other halide ion, wholly (Br^-) or partly (I^-). The greater suppression of Br^- ion adsorption is consistent with the standard oxidation potentials of the electrodes $Ag, AgX(s), X^-$, the values being -0.073 V for $X = Br$ and $+0.1522$ V for $X = I$.

These results are in conformity with the earlier data⁷ on the kinetics of the desorption of Br^- ions, adsorbed on Ag, in $10^{-3}M$ NaI. The nearly total desorption of Br^- ions was completed in about 30 min for the 1, 5 and 20 layer-thicknesses studied.

(B) *Adsorption on aluminium of Br^- and I^- ions*: The adsorption rate-isotherm for I^- ions on aluminium shows that the rate is fairly uniform. The maximum layers obtained are 8 in 200 hr. The bromide ion adsorption also shows a similar behaviour, the rate being slightly greater than that of I^- ion adsorption. Both the isotherms in general show a tendency towards slow saturation. In the competitive adsorption of Br^- and I^- ions on aluminium from a mixed adsorbate, a similar mutual suppression effect is observed. The

adsorption of bromide ions is suppressed by 90% while that of iodide ions is suppressed by 80% (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Rates of adsorption on aluminium of (i) (A) Br⁻, (B) I⁻, (C) Cl⁻ from 10⁻³M NaBr, NaI, NaCl solutions respectively, (ii) (D) Br⁻, (E) I⁻ from (NaBr+NaI) solution, (iii) (F) I⁻ from (NaI+NaCl) solution. All solutions of pH = 3.5 and *t* = 30°.

Experiments on the desorption of I⁻ and Br⁻ ions adsorbed on aluminium, in 10⁻³M solutions of NaBr and NaI respectively, are consistent with the mutual suppression effect. The relative ease of desorption of I⁻ ions, adsorbed on aluminium, in solutions of NaBr and NaCl compared to the non-desorbability of I⁻ ions adsorbed on silver⁶ suggests a weaker attachment of I⁻ ions on aluminium surface compared to that on silver surface.

(C) *Adsorption on aluminium of Cl⁻ and I⁻ ions*: The adsorption rate-isotherms of Cl⁻ and I⁻ ions on aluminium differ appreciably. The adsorption of Cl⁻ ions is very slow, the maximum adsorption of monolayer taking place in 100 hr. The adsorption of I⁻ ions on the other hand is comparatively faster. In general, the rates of adsorption, (R) on aluminium and silver of Cl⁻, Br⁻ and I⁻ ions, taken individually, are in the order R_{Br} > R_I > R_{Cl}. Results of competitive adsorption of Cl⁻ and I⁻ ions on aluminium show that the adsorption of Cl⁻ and I⁻ ions is nearly completely suppressed (≥ 99%). The total adsorption of I⁻ ions in the mixture hardly exceeds about 0.13 layer in 200 hr, that of Cl⁻ ion being

undetectably low. These results agree with our earlier data⁷ regarding the exchange desorption rates of Cl^- ions, adsorbed on aluminium, in $\text{NaI } 10^{-3}M$ solution.

Results on the kinetics of desorption are presented in Table 1. The curves are similar in nature to those obtained in the case of desorption of Br^- ions (mono-layer)

TABLE 1

Rate constants for desorption of monomolecular layer of I^- ions adsorbed on aluminium

Medium $10^{-3}M$	Rate constant k (min^{-1}) $\times 10^3$	
	segment I	segment II
NaI	5.8	0.9
NaBr	12.0	1.6
NaCl	4.9	0.4

on silver⁷. Generally, there are two values for the rate constant (k) in any medium, the initial value is always greater, showing that desorption rates are faster in the beginning and subsequently slow down. The rate constants are in the order $k(\text{NaBr}) > k(\text{NaI}) > k(\text{NaCl})$ for both the segments. No measurable desorption is observed in water.

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